

Latest news from the solar g modes

(how we measured the rapid core rotation)

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Helioseismology

Internal rotation

Echelle diagramme

GOLF 20.5 years (rebinned 10 points)

Method: (similar to) ultrasonic scan

- Idea: identify a differential p-mode parameter and use it for the detection of a collective signature of g-modes, all together, in the very low frequency asymptotic regime!

G-mode asymptotic (approximate) properties

- Degree by degree, splitting independent of radial order
- But splitting different for different degrees, modified by a Coriolis coefficient, $(1-1/(l+1))$, i.e. 0.5 for $l=1$, and 5/6 pour $l=2$
- For degree, periods are équidistant,

$$P_{n,l} = P_l(|n| + 1/2 + \theta) + O(1/P_{n,l})$$

where P_l is the equidistant period spacing defined by:

$$P_l = P_0 / \sqrt{l(l+1)}$$

- The best models predict a value of P_0 of about 34 ± 1 min.
- It implies period equidistances $P_1 \approx 24$ min and $P_2 \approx 14$ min.

Data set used: 16.5-year of full disk
measurements by GOLF 1996 – 2012,
96% filling

Mean of 36161 p-mode spectra computed on 8 hours between 2.3 et 3.7 mHz

The same approximately flattened

An example of 8 h

Its spectrum

End of first step: These are the 36131 values of $T(t)$ fluctuations, sampled at 4-hour intervals, and limited at ± 240 s.

There are 34261 non zero values, and their rms deviation is 52 s.

2nd step : power spectrum of T(t)

Most interesting is the almost absence of a low frequency tendency in $1/f$ that opens the hope for success.

Model of 75 modes of degree 1

Possible model of g modes of degrees 1 and 2

Its autocorrelation in the range 6 – 30 μHz

Same model, deeply embedded in a lot of noise

Autocorrelation of (model + noise)

Search for a splitting signature in the autocorrelation of the large separation spectrum

The g-mode splitting equations present a very peculiar specificity in the case of our measurement:

$$s(1,m)=m(\Omega/2 - \omega) \text{ nHz [1]}$$

$$s(2,m)=m(5\Omega/6 - \omega) \text{ nHz. [2]}$$

Usually, $\omega = 31\text{nHz}$ (one year period)

Here we must understand that $\omega = 433 \text{ nHz}$ (sidereal rotation of our « instrument », which is the set of full disk p modes)

Consequence of Equation (1) :

$$s(1,1) = (\Omega/2 - 433) \text{ nHz}$$

$s(1,1)$ is negative if $\Omega < 866$ nHz

But the autocorrelation does not see a difference between a positive and a negative splitting

There could be two different rotations rates Ω providing the same splitting $s(1,1)$

With our peak at 209 nHz, the choice is $\Omega \approx 446$ nHz or $\Omega \approx 1282$ nHz

Test of $A(s(1,1) + A(2,1) + A(s(2,2))$ as a function of Ω

next step: search for the asymptotic equidistance period spacing

example: the “easy” case of $\ell=1$

- We look for an equidistance of 24 to 25 minutes
- We know the splitting: 210 nHz
- We can then test a model of many g modes triplets in our frequency range 5.5 – 34 μHz with 2 free parameters: equidistance and position
- Caution: high density of modes in the very low frequencies. The best results are obtained by starting near 7 μHz

Mean of 76 spectrum layers separated by 1443 s in periods

Cross-correlation model-spectrum for $\ell=1$

Complete model including $\ell=1, 2, 3$ and 4

Its cross-correlation with the large separation spectrum

S/N = 12 !!!

With the mean of 3 spectra and the model including only $l=1$ central frequencies

With the mean of 3 spectra and a model including only $l=1$ split frequencies

Main results

- We have now in hands:
- 4 asymptotic equidistances, slightly different, all measured within about 1 second
- 2 equations describing the small departures from equidistance for $\ell=1$ and $\ell=2$
- 4 measurements of the mean g-mode kernels rotation, again slightly different, all measured within about 1 nHz, say as precisely as the surface rotation !
- A rapid core rotation, averaging at one-week period, which means a vertical gradient of 4000 km/h between core and envelope. How sharp is this “second tachocline” ?
- Difficulty of understanding the process that makes these modes so clearly detected, as well as their distributions of amplitudes, with degree and tesseral order.

Thanks for your attention

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